

METHODS OF USING GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN LESSONS IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Annotation: The article examines the problem of developing gaming technologies for teaching in primary school. The scientific work shows the main aspects of the use of gaming technologies in lessons in primary school. The use of games has been proven to promote cognitive development in elementary school students.

Key words: primary school, game, gaming technology, classification of games, lesson, educational process.

Introduction. The development of society and education in the twentieth century poses the question of how to interest modern children in learning. Modern schools focus on using all possible technologies, methods and resources to enhance the cognitive activity of schoolchildren [3, 4, 6]. Such means of training and education include gaming technologies. The use of gaming technologies in the educational process of schools until recently was quite limited. Today, the use of games in school is a necessary component, because modern children are characterized by increased excitability, emotionality, fairly rapid fatigue, instability of attention, situational behavior, and games can stabilize this situation [1, 2, 5]. Analysis of the latest research and publications. Both foreign (J. Komensky, J. Locke, J.-J. Rousseau, G. Spencer, F. Schiller) and domestic (I. Ivanov, A. . Makarenko, V. Tersky). A high assessment of educational and pedagogical games as one of the methods of active learning and training of future graduates is given in

the works of A. Verbitsky, L. Vishnyakova, R. Zhukov, D. Elkonin and other modern scientists, researchers and teaching practitioners.

At the present stage of development of education, an important place is occupied by the introduction and development of the concept of a modern school, which provides for the comprehensive development of students in the context of developing ten important competencies in them [7, 8, 11]. Learning at school occurs through the use of different technologies. Psychologists note that schools devote very little space to play, immediately imposing on the child an approach to any activity using the methods of an adult. Schools use such programs, the implementation of which allocates little time for play and recreation for students [9, 10]. Since the transition from play to serious activities is too abrupt, children do not have time to switch from one type of activity to another and relax. Therefore, the game should become an important component of the activities of primary school students [14].

Modern educational standards of the school require the education of a comprehensively developed personality with key competencies, such as communication in the state language, communication in foreign languages, mathematical literacy, competence in natural sciences and technologies, information and digital competence, the ability to learn throughout life, social and public competences, entrepreneurship, general cultural literacy, environmental literacy and healthy life [12, 13]. In this regard, primary school teachers are increasingly interested in the question of how to choose from a rich arsenal of teaching methods and techniques those that would encourage the active acquisition of knowledge and skills.

The transition from preschool childhood, where play dominates, to school life, where learning plays a decisive role, must be pedagogically thoughtful. The definition of children's development indicates that mental processes develop more effectively in play than in other types of activities, therefore, relying on play is the most important way to include younger schoolchildren in educational activities [12,

13]. Play is one of the most interesting types of human activity, the leading activity of children and a method of education [15, 17].

Game as a social phenomenon that arose in the process of historical development of mankind from labor actions, reflects reality, and is improved with the development of “man-society” relations. Play is an active, conscious, purposeful activity that embodies the child’s need for activity [18]. The emergence of play is due to the development of society and is associated with changes in the child’s position in the system of social relations. This concept of the origin of play cannot be considered exhaustive, since according to it, only the desire to participate in the work of adults encourages play. This means that, having joined such activities quite early, the child will exhaust his need for play by real participation in the life of adults and will not play [16]. One of the founders of game theory was the German philosopher, psychologist, author of the famous works “Animal Games” and “Human Games” Karl Gross (1861–1946). Based on comparisons of the characteristics of the play activity of children and the instinctive activity of young animals, he argued that play has a biological nature and is one of the ways of preparing for future serious activity, the main content of a child’s life. However, K. Gross overestimated the instinctive nature of play and identified the play of a child and an animal [7, 11].

Modern psychological and pedagogical research into play is characterized by a convergence of views on it as the leading activity of preschool children, an analysis of its educational capabilities and means of their actualization. L. Vygotsky and the scientists who represent his school (D. Elkonin, O. Usova) focused on these problems. They convinced that the educational potential of the game could only be realized if it was directed by adults. This point of view was developed in the works of the French psychologist A. Wallon, it was also supported by representatives of pedagogical science: R. Pfütze, I. Hoppe, L. Schreuter (Germany), D. Kovacs, O. Vág, P. Bakony (Hungary), L. Belinova (Czech Republic), E. Petrova, S. Avramova (Bulgaria).

The use of gaming technologies affects the development of psychological flexibility, emancipation, sociability, and emotional and volitional influence. The child has the right to make mistakes in the game. It is a means of developing children's imagination, develops cognitive abilities, the emotional side of the personality, and enriches vocabulary. It is in play that different aspects of a child's personality are revealed and developed, and many intellectual and emotional needs are satisfied [3, 11].

In elementary grades, a game makes it easy to attract attention and maintain students' interest for a long time in important and complex objects, properties and phenomena, on which under normal conditions it is not always possible to focus everyone's attention [5, 9]. The use of games in the educational process of school is justified from psychological points, because by taking certain game roles, acting out the corresponding relationships during the game, the child creates himself as a subject of a specific activity. The technology of game learning is such an organization of the educational process, during which learning is carried out in the process of including students in the game [8, 17] .

Educational games have a goal, in addition to mastering educational material, the formation of skills and abilities, and providing the student with the opportunity to self-determinate, the development of creative abilities that contribute to the emotional perception of the learning content. Games are extremely diverse in content, character, and organization, so their exact classification causes many difficulties; to a large extent, it is quite arbitrary. Gaming learning technologies play an important role in ensuring student self-realization because:

- this is a well-known, familiar and favorite form of activity for people of all ages;
 - This is an effective means of activation. The game makes it easier to overcome difficulties, obstacles, and psychological barriers;
- is motivation by nature. Regarding cognitive activity, it requires students to have initiative, creativity, imagination, and determination;

- this is the transfer of knowledge, skills and abilities at the “student-to-student” level;

- it is multifunctional, its influence on the student cannot be limited to one aspect;

- it is predominantly a collective, group form of work, which is based on competitions. The competitor can be the student himself (convincing himself, improving his results) or another student;

- it has the final didactic result.

- it has a clearly defined goal and pedagogical result.

Systematic use of games increases the effectiveness of learning. The success of using games depends on the atmosphere of necessary verbal communication created by the teacher in the classroom. It is important that students get used to such communication, become interested and become participants in this process together with the teacher. When organizing didactic games, you need to think through the following questions of methodology:

- The goal of the game.

- What skills and abilities in the field of English will schoolchildren learn during the game?

- Which moment of the game should you pay special attention to?

- What other educational goals are pursued during the game?

- Number of players.

- What materials and aids will be needed for the game?

- How to familiarize children with the rules of the game with the least amount of time?

- How long should the game last?

- Will it be interesting and exciting?

- Will the students want to return to it again?

- How to organize observation of children to find out whether everyone is involved in the game?

- What changes can be made to the game to increase children's interest and activity?

- What conclusions should be communicated to students at the end, after the game (the best moments of the game, shortcomings in the game, the results of mastering linguistic knowledge) [4].

However, there are also limitations for conducting didactic games:

1. You should not organize an educational game if students do not know the topic well enough.
2. It is inappropriate to introduce games into tests and exams if they were not used in the learning process.
3. Games should not be used in subjects and program topics where they cannot give a positive result.

When organizing didactic games, the following provisions must be observed:

1. The rules of the game should be simple, clearly formulated, and the content of the proposed linguistic material should be understandable to schoolchildren.
2. The game should provide grounds for mental activity.
3. Didactic material used during the game should be easy to use.
4. Each student must be an active participant in the game. Long waits for your turn to join the game reduce interest in it.
5. If several games are played in a lesson, then light and heavy games should alternate in terms of educational content.

Conclusions. So, a game is one of the special means that a teacher uses every day in lessons in elementary school. It is also worth remembering that the game helps the teacher in teaching children, and encourages students to quickly memorize the material. A teacher using games in English lessons must comply with the above requirements. And make the game interesting and involve all children in the work. In order for the game to be carried out methodically correctly and give a positive result, the teacher needs to know all the stages of the formation of the game. Also, the teacher should distinguish games by degree of difficulty and only then demonstrate and conduct them in front of the children. In addition, teachers must

control the actions of students, and not just wait for the result, because often in the game children learn material that they should know well.

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